

TECHNOLOGY OF BREAD PRODUCT PRODUCTION BY ENRICHING WHEAT FLOUR WITH SOYBEAN FLOUR

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Abstract: This study is devoted to the study of the technology of production of high-protein bakery products by enriching wheat flour with soybean flour. The presence of 35–45% protein, essential amino acids, phosphorus, calcium and B-group vitamins in soybean flour indicates that it is an important raw material for enriching food products

Keywords: wheat flour, soybean flour, enriched bread, protein content, rheological properties, functional food.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено изучению технологии производства высокобелковых хлебобулочных изделий путем обогащения пшеничной муки соевой мукой. Наличие 35–45% белка, незаменимых аминокислот, фосфора, кальция и витаминов группы В в соевой муке свидетельствует о том, что она является важным сырьем для обогащения пищевых продуктов.

Ключевые слова: пшеничная мука, соевая мука, обогащенный хлеб, содержание белка, реологические свойства, функциональные продукты питания.

Nowadays, the rapid growth of the world population, food shortages and protein deficiency problems are becoming acute problems on a global scale. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 800 million people in developing countries cannot fully meet their physiological needs for protein. This situation is especially manifested as a specific problem in regions where the main source of food is bread and flour products. Wheat bread products are the main food products widely consumed around the world. At the same time, bread made from wheat flour has a low content of lysine and threonine amino acids, which limits the nutritional value of the product. Therefore, increasing its biological value by using additional protein-rich raw materials in bread making is an urgent scientific and practical issue. Soybean (*Glycine max*) is considered the most valuable source of protein in the world, containing 35-45% protein, 18-22% fat, essential amino acids, vitamins and minerals. The amino acid composition of

soy protein includes all the essential amino acids necessary for the human body, and its biological value is very high. The experience of countries where the technology of preparing bread products by mixing soy flour with wheat flour has been developed shows that the nutritional value of such products is significantly higher than that of conventional bread. The grain and flour industry in Uzbekistan is one of the main components of national food security. Every year, 6-7 million tons of bread and bakery products are consumed in our country. Therefore, the study and implementation of the technology of enriching bakery products by adding soy flour is of great importance not only from a scientific, but also from an economic and social point of view. Traditional bread products made from wheat flour have several nutritional deficiencies: low content of the amino acid lysine, low biological value, low amounts of calcium and iron. This is especially problematic for children, pregnant women and the elderly. Adding soy flour makes it possible to eliminate these deficiencies, but at the same time it can change the rheological properties of the dough and complicate the technological process. Today, bread products in the food industry constitute the main part of people's daily diet. However, breads made from traditional wheat flour are mainly rich in carbohydrates, and they are relatively low in protein, vitamins and minerals. This situation can have a certain negative impact on the complete and balanced nutrition of the population. At the same time, the demand for healthy eating among modern consumers is growing. In particular, the need for bread products with high biological value, rich in protein, dietary and functional properties has increased significantly. Therefore, enriching the composition of bakery products and increasing their nutritional value has become an urgent issue. Soy flour is very rich in protein, and it contains amino acids, vitamins (group B) and minerals necessary for the human body. Mixing it with wheat flour increases the biological value of the bakery product. However, since the technological properties of soy flour differ from wheat flour, the viscosity, elasticity and fermentation process of the dough may change. This affects the volume, porosity and overall quality of the finished product. Therefore, determining the optimal proportions for the preparation of bakery products by enriching wheat flour with soy flour, setting up technological processes correctly and obtaining a high-quality product is an important scientific and practical problem. Research in this area serves to develop the food industry and improve public health. In the scientific literature, there is a lack of sufficiently comprehensive research to determine the optimal addition ratio of soy flour to wheat flour, and to study the effect of added soy flour on the physicochemical,

rheological and organoleptic properties of dough and bread products. Therefore, there is a need for in-depth scientific research to solve this problem. The aim of the research is to develop a technology for the production of high-nutritional value bakery products based on the enrichment of wheat flour with soy flour and to study the physicochemical, rheological and organoleptic characteristics of the finished product. Also, one of the important goals of the research is to increase the biological value of enriched bakery products, improve their quality indicators and determine the optimal amount of soy flour addition. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set: to study the chemical composition and nutritional value of wheat grain and wheat flour; to analyze the composition of soy flour, its amino acid balance and biological value; to study the scientific and theoretical foundations of the enrichment of wheat flour with soy flour; to prepare mixtures with the addition of soy flour in different amounts (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) to wheat flour; to develop a technology for the production of bakery products based on the prepared mixtures; to determine the rheological properties of the dough, including elasticity, viscosity and gas-holding capacity; Study of physicochemical parameters of finished bakery products; assessment of nutritional and energy value of enriched bakery products; determination of the effect of adding soy flour on the quantity and quality of gluten; analysis of organoleptic parameters of finished products; determination of the optimal ratio for wheat-soy flour mixtures and assessment of the practical significance of the developed technology. Wheat is the most widespread and ancient crop on Earth. Archaeological data indicate that wheat was an important food product of the sedentary population in Asia Minor 8000 years ago. Iraq, Egypt, China, Northern Mesopotamia are among the most ancient regions where wheat was cultivated. In Central Asia, it began to be cultivated in the Neolithic period in the 7th millennium BC. This period is known as the Zaytun farming culture. (V. Ya. Masson, 1971). In the 7th - 5th millennium BC, cereal crops, including wheat, were grown on the plains between the Kopet-Dag ridge network and the Karakum barrens, using only atmospheric precipitation and without artificial irrigation. In the fertile lands of the lower reaches of the Amu Darya, the Fergana and Hissar valleys, the Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya and Vakhsh basins, highly developed irrigated agriculture with complex irrigation canal systems existed in the 2nd millennium BC and wheat was grown. The largest areas of wheat cultivation are located in Russia, the USA, China, India, Canada, Argentina, France, Turkey, Australia, Kazakhstan, and Italy. Wheat is the main food crop in most countries of the world. More than half of the world's population consumes it. It is cultivated in the world

from the northern polar regions to the southernmost borders of five continents. As a food crop, wheat has many natural advantages. Its grain is nutritious, high-calorie, well stored, transported, and processed to obtain high-quality products. Wheat flour is widely used in the baking and confectionery industry to prepare various easily digestible delicacies. Cereals, pasta, vermicelli and other products are made from the grain. Wheat bran, straw, straw, and husk have high nutritional value. Its bran is a highly concentrated feed for all farm animals. Bran is also used to prepare mixed feed. The amount of digestible protein in it is 1.5 times higher than that of barley grain. Straw, crushed and steamed or treated with chemicals, is a delicious food for cattle and sheep. 100 kg of straw contains 0.5 - 1.0 kg of digestible protein, 20 - 22 nutritional units. In addition, straw is used as a building material, as bedding for cattle, and in the production of paper. It is a good food for cattle. Unlike other plant products, one of the most important indicators of the quality of wheat grain is its protein and gluten content. When yeast is added to the dough, it increases in volume and forms carbon dioxide gas. Wheat grain contains starch, protein, minerals, vitamins. Minerals and vitamins in wheat are especially abundant in whole grain and enriched flour products, and they have a high nutritional value. As a food product, wheat flour is used to make various types of bread, pastries, cookies, biscuits, cakes, pies, waffles, ice cream cups, pasta, cereals used in the preparation of dietary food for children, semi-finished products and other products. Various lagmans, kulchatoy, sauces, candies and drinks, sumalak are made from it. Grains with germinated bran are used as medicinal products. The chemical composition of wheat grain is very variable. Its protein, gluten, minerals, vitamins, pigments and enzymes vary depending on the climate, soil and fertilizers applied, the agricultural techniques used, and the varieties. According to the requirements of the world standard, the protein content of wheat grain should not be less than 13.5%. The protein content of wheat grain determines its use. For baking bread, the grain should contain 14-15% protein, and for making pasta, 17-18% protein. The main source of plant protein for humans is wheat grain, which satisfies 50% of the daily protein requirement. The protein complex in the endosperm of the grain consists mainly of gliadin and glutenin, and in the bran - albumin and globulins, the latter of which do not form gluten. Gliadin and glutenin form gluten. In determining the baking properties of wheat flour, the quantity and quality of gluten, which affects the volume, porosity, and spreadability of bread, are of great importance. The high volume of bread depends on the elasticity of gluten and the ability of the dough to retain gas. The baking properties of wheat depend not only on the amount of

protein and gluten in the grain, but also on the quality of gluten. If the gluten elongation is not higher than 30 cm and not less than 20 cm or the IDK-1 index is 45-75, it is considered to be of good quality. Bread spreadability is a measure of bread

Conclusion

As a result of rheological and technological analyses, it was found that increasing the amount of soy flour directly affects the dough structure. While a significant weakening of the gluten network was observed in the range of 20–25%, the range of 10–15% was determined as the optimal zone for maintaining technological stability. Analysis of the physicochemical parameters of the finished bread product showed that the addition of soy flour significantly improves the biological value of the product by increasing its moisture, acidity and protein content, while not exceeding the regulatory requirements.

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